

The space program of Turkiye

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“The only way to ensure justice in the world is to exist in space in a powerful manner”

Recep Tayyip Erdogan (February 2021)

Abstract

From the launch of the first satellites (1950s) to the modern era, progress in the exploration and exploitation of space for political, scientific and military purposes has been rapid. As access to space becomes more affordable, so too does the effort of states to exploit it.

In addition, space is considered one of the dimensions of the unified battlefield and its use can give a military force significant advantages.

The 10 objectives of the Turkish space program emphatically state that Turkey is seeking a new, upgraded role in the world. Despite the fact that the development of autonomous space capabilities by Ankara requires significant funding, which is seriously hampered by the serious problems of the Turkish economy (high inflation, devaluation of the national currency, etc.), the main axes of the Turkish space program are being implemented, albeit with a delay.

Taking into account Turkey's capabilities in the space sector, the development of national space capabilities by our country (Greece) in the field of telecommunications and earth observation satellites is a one-way street, in order to compensate significantly for the advantages that the Turkish Armed Forces (TAF), currently possess.

Keywords:

Turkiye, National Space Program, Autonomous Space Capabilities, Soft Power

1. Introduction

From the time of the launch of the first satellites¹ and the subsequent rivalry between the two superpowers, the USA and the former USSR, to modern times, progress in the exploration and exploitation of space for political, scientific and military purposes has been and remains rapid.

Moreover, space is considered one of the dimensions of the modern unified battlefield, hence it should be taken into account in the planning and conduct of operations, since they depend on the exploitation of the capabilities provided by existing satellite systems, which gives significant advantages to a military force that exploits it.

A characteristic example of the importance of space is the continuous increase in investments, at the level of governments worldwide, which for the year 2024 amounted to approximately 135 billion dollars², representing a 10% increase compared to 2023. Of the above amount, spending related to defense constitutes the majority of budgets (\$73 billion, percentage 54%), underlining the strategic importance of space.

Figure 1: Government Space Programs (GSP). Amounts in millions of dollars. Source: Novaspac

¹ On 04 October 1957 the first satellite (SPUTNIK-1) was launched by the USSR

² **Source:** <https://nova.space/press-release/defense-spending-drives-government-space-budgets-to-historic-high>

The main reasons for the surge in investment in space programs are:

- Space programs do indeed have very high costs for countries budgets. However, the achievements, fame and power gained as a result of implementing such programs, make the costs negligible.

- Space programs increase the geographical value of countries, add to their technological capabilities, strengthen their economies and international partnerships, and enhance their reputation on the international stage.

- Space activities enhance innovation, paving the way for the use of new inventions and technologies in various fields. As space programs are not limited to space, they increase employment and productivity in all sectors.

- Space-related activities make people's lives easier in many ways, including:

- With the production of microscale satellites, observation has become possible, increasing productivity in many sectors, especially in the agricultural sector.
- Thanks to the capabilities of observation satellites, it is now possible to monitor natural resources, transport networks, etc., in real time.
- Remote sensing satellites provide real-time information for national defense purposes (intelligence gathering, early warning of missile threats, targeting, etc.).
- Communication satellites are also used to transmit TV and radio signals and in other communication sectors-areas (civil-military), such as internet access.
- In the near future, communication satellites will allow access to high-speed internet connections everywhere in the world.
- Location and time information can be collected at any time in the world in a fast and accurate way.
- In the coming years the space economy will further develop in areas such as space tourism, space mining, etc.

2. Brief History

Turkey's satellite program was launched in 1989 and aimed at acquiring national capabilities in the field of satellite communications. In this context, Turkey has been developing the TÜRKSAT program since the 1990s when it launched its first communication satellite named TÜRKSAT-1A on 24 Jan 94, but it crashed into the sea

about 12 minutes after the launch due to a problem with the launch vehicle's propulsion rocket.

In the same year Turkey launched the communications satellite TÜRKSAT-1B, and in 1996 it launched a satellite of the same type, TÜRKSAT-1C. The above satellites ceased operations in 2006 and 2010, respectively. Since 1995, the Turkish government set the objective of establishing a central structure for space policy-making, followed by political processes, proposals, decisions and bills, which came to fruition on 13 Dec 18, when a Presidential Decree established the establishment and operation of the Turkish Space Agency (Türkiye Uzay Ajansı/TÜA).

TÜA is the government agency for national aerospace research. It is based in Ankara and comes under the Ministry of Science and Technology. With its establishment, the Department of Aviation and Space Technologies in the Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure was abolished. TÜA prepares strategic plans that include medium and long-term goals and priorities, key principles and methods to be followed and resource allocation for aerospace science and technologies. TÜA co-operates closely with the TÜBİTAK (Space Technology Research Institute).

The main institutions and companies involved in Turkish satellite programs and space policy, apart from TUA, are TAI, ASELSAN and the Turkish Defense Industry Presidency (SSB), with the latter two companies having a major role in satellite programs used for military purposes.

On 09 Feb 21, Turkish President R.T. Erdogan presented the National Space Program at the Turkish Presidency's Conference and Cultural Center (BEŞTEPE MİLLET KONGRE VE KÜLTÜR MERKEZİ). The main objectives of the Turkish Space Program are:

- On the 100th anniversary of the establishment of the Republic of Turkey, participation of a Turkish astronaut in an international space mission.
- Establishment of a satellite production company.
- Establishment of a launch site within the Turkish territory and on the territory of a third country (Somalia).
- Increase in space capabilities through research and development of expertise in space weather and meteorology.
- Development of an Earth-based meteor and planetary observation capability.
- Conduct integrated studies by the space industry.
- Establishment of a space center and a space technology development zone.
- Providing undergraduate and postgraduate space education.
- Creation of Turkish GPS.

Figure 2: The 10 objectives of Turkey's space program. Source: Anadolu News Agency.

3. Recent Developments

3.1 Satellite Launches

The developments of the last five years regarding the launch of Turkish satellites are as follows:

- In 2021, 2 communication satellites were launched, TÜRKSAT-5A (08 Jan 2021) and TÜRKSAT-5B (20 Dec 2021). TÜRKSAT-5B was launched in December 2021 from Florida, USA on SpaceX's FALCON 9 rocket and serves as a backup for the TÜRKSAT-3A (launched in 2008) and TÜRKSAT-4A (launched in 2014) satellites.

Figures 3-4: The communications satellites TÜRKSAT-5A and 5B Source: TUA

- On 24 Jan 21 the launch of the domestic mini observation satellite ASELSAT-3U took place. The launch was carried out by the American private company SpaceX. ASELSAT-3U collects data on the space environment and transmits them to a ground station.

Photo 5: The ASELSAT-3U satellite Source: TÜA

- On 13 Jan 22, the experimental satellite Pocket Qube (5X5X5 cm and weight 237 grams), a Turkish-made experimental satellite called Grizu-263A, was launched from Cape Canaveral, USA. The satellite was designed by the Grizu-263 Space Team of the Faculty of Engineering of Bulent Ecevit University (BEU).

Photo 6: The Grizu-263A nanosatellite Source: NanoSats Database

- On 15 Apr 23 earth observation satellite IMECE (built by the Turkish company TUBITAK UZAY) was launched.

Photo 7: IMECE earth observation satellite Source: TÜA

- On 09 July 24 the communications satellite TURKSAT-6A (built by the Turkish company TÜBITAK UZAY) was launched.

Photo 8: The communications satellite TÜRKSAT-6A Source: TÜBITAK UZAY

-On 14 Jan 25, Fergani Space, a company founded in 2022 by Selcuk Bayraktar, President of the Turkish company Baykar (manufacturer of the BAYRAKTAR and AKINCI UAVs), announced the successful launch of the FGN-100-d1 satellite from the Vandenberg space base in the USA. The 102-kilogram satellite is part of Fergani Space's ambitious Positioning Satellite Constellation Project.

FGN-100-d1 was launched along with other satellites as part of the Transporter-12 mission, through a Rideshare program. Its operation began immediately, transmitting telemetry data and implementing the first step of an ambitious plan to complete a Turkish geolocation satellite system.

Photo 9: The FGN-100d1 satellite. Source: FERGANI SPACE

Turkey has so far launched a total of:

- Eleven (11) communication satellites, of which 6 are in operation (TÜRKSAT-3A/4A/4B.5A,5B and 6A).
- Five (5) earth observation satellites, of which 3 are operational (GÖTURK I and 2, IMECE).
- Three (3) satellites of various types (ASELSAT-3U, GRIZU-263A and FGN-100d1), which are in operation.

It is worth noting that both the communication satellites and the remote sensing satellites have a dual use since they are used for civil and military purposes (a percentage of their resources, which varies depending on the satellite, is used exclusively by the Turkish Armed Forces).

3.2 Staff Training

In the context of making the Turkish space program as independent as possible from foreign sources, Turkey has sought and is seeking to train appropriate personnel in space technology. Thus, postgraduate space degree programs have been established at the Turkish Aviation Academy as well as Know How Technology Transfer programs from the British SSTL (Surrey Satellite Technology Ltd). At the same time, TÜBİTAK funds scholarships for postgraduate and doctoral studies abroad (TÜBİTAK BİDEB 2213 and 2230 Scholarship Programs).

3.3 Creation of a Space Station in Somalia

According to Turkish and international media, Turkey will build a space station in Somalia to carry out missile tests and long-range launches.

The decision to build this facility in Somalia is attributed to its proximity to the equator, a location that is advantageous for missile launches due to its lower fuel requirements and better payload capacity. Somalia is one of the three ideal locations for launches near the equator, along with Kazakhstan's Baikonur Cosmodrome and the launch complexes used by NASA and SpaceX in Florida, USA.

The planned project follows a maritime exploration agreement in the African country's EEZ by a Turkish seismic survey ship and marks a deepening of relations between the two countries. It will be recalled that Turkey has built and operates a large military base in Somalia.

4. Future Developments

Turkey remains committed to its space program in all areas of space applications, building and designing new satellites for both civil and military purposes. At the same time, it is seeking to develop indigenous capabilities in areas where it does not yet have sufficient expertise.

In particular, Turkey has for years set itself the goal of acquiring autonomous space capabilities in at least two areas, the development of satellite platforms and the development of payloads for communications, reconnaissance (optical, IR and RADAR) and tracking/navigation purposes.

Its intention is that by 2028 it will be able to use its own satellite launchers in order not to be dependent on other countries or private companies. The rockets are planned to be launched from the space station to be built in Somalia, as mentioned above.

The Turkish space program has as its main future goal the landing of an unmanned spacecraft with a national hybrid rocket. In this context, a test vertical launch of a hybrid rocket carrier (SORS) was successfully carried out on 19 Jul 21. The launch was carried out from Sinope, while the first vertical propulsion test of the SORS hybrid rocket carrier was carried out on 11 Apr 21.

The ultimate goal of the space program is to send a Turkish astronaut into space or to carry out a Turkish scientific mission to the Moon, manned or unmanned, within the current decade.

As far as the creation of a Turkish GPS is concerned, the milestone is the launch of the FGN-100d1 satellite, while the desired end state is the ability to provide dedicated positioning information in areas such as transport, communications and military operations.

For the coming years there are plans for the new TÜRKSAT 7 series of telecommunications satellites, as well as new telecommunications satellites, both in geostationary and earth orbit. As far as new systems are concerned, an exclusively military telecommunications satellite for use by the TEDs only (MAHU: Milli Askeri Haberleşme Uydusu) is already in the planning stage. For the first time, the military satellite will have UHF-Band and EHF-Band transponders developed by ASELSAN.

Another area under consideration is the development of a Space Surveillance System. This system is related to ground-based space surveillance which is necessary for those countries that have made a significant investment in their space infrastructure, since satellites are valuable assets that need to be protected from a number of events such as collision with each other, avoidance of space debris, etc. For this reason, Turkey, like other countries, and the EU (with the Space Situational Awareness-SSA system) intends to develop a space situational awareness capability by deploying ground-based RADARs.

TÜBİTAK UZAY (SPACE), with the experience gained from the management of earth observation satellites, has a national program underway to develop ground stations for earth observation satellites [Milli Yer İstasyonu Gelistirme Projesi (MİYEG)]. The aim of this program is also to develop a station that will be able to cooperate with all types of satellites.

5. Capabilities - Advantages at Military Level

Turkey's space program and in particular the capabilities provided to the Turkish Armed Forces, the services of Turkish satellites, give significant advantages both in the planning and in the phase of conducting operations, such as:

- Communication satellites provide the possibility of continuous communication of troops and assets, regardless of the communication difficulty and distance. They are an important part of the Command, Control, Communications and Intelligence (C3I) function which aims to ensure uninterrupted communications in the theatre of operations with high security. Timely transmission of orders ensures a common understanding of the current operational situation and contributes to effective Command and Control. It promotes interoperability since everyone communicates with everyone in a short time. This ensures short response times, seamless flow of information and timely information for decision making, achieving centralised control and decentralised execution.

- The use of communication satellites provides the possibility of becoming independent of vulnerable and expensive land lines, coupling nodes or submerged submarine cables and relay stations, which require high maintenance costs in peacetime and can be destroyed either by attack or sabotage in times of operations.

- The use of TÜRKSAT telecommunication satellites by the Turkish Armed Forces units ensures the ability to transfer tactical data and imagery over the horizon, under any conditions, from multiple platforms (e.g., aircraft, FMS) and to any Command and Control Centre. Satellite linking capabilities upgrade the operational capabilities of Turkish UAVs (UAVs) by increasing the range of action by ensuring deep penetration missions beyond the horizon (BEYOND LINE OF SIGHT - LOS). This facilitates intelligence gathering and early threat detection, while providing the military hierarchy with the ability to fully understand the current joint operational picture in a short time, which in turn facilitates the decision-making process and the conduct of operations.

- The uninterrupted operation of satellite telecommunications by the TDFs, and indeed in a secure manner, enables military units and assets to be deployed over long distances from their bases, especially in isolated areas, thus extending their area of operations.

- Peacetime remote sensing satellites have been contributing to the collection of information on the enemy by obtaining high-resolution satellite images. Satellite images provide information on terrain, layout and facilities, thus facilitating the targeting process. At the same time, the use of national remote sensing satellites ensures secrecy as to the type of information nationally sought.

- In times of crisis, remote sensing satellites enable early detection of any military preparations, troop movements and asset redeployments, revealing enemy intentions and movements, thus contributing to the prevention of strategic surprise.

- In the course of operations, early identification of the battle layout enables the disclosure of enemy intentions and feeds back the targeting process, especially when identifying high value and priority targets, while facilitating the assessment of post-attack effects (Battle Damage Assessment - BDA). Military installations, defensive protection assets and critical infrastructure (power stations, oil refineries, airports, bridges, telecommunication infrastructure, etc.) are identified and inter-agency coordination is facilitated.

- Possible future use by the Turkish Armed Forces of new satellite systems capable of providing GPS services will enable complete independence from third country satellites and ensure uninterrupted operational use of high-tech and lethal GPS/INS-guided missiles and munitions.

6. Capabilities at Political Level

Turkey, as part of its strategic goal to become a global power, has expanded the coverage area of its telecommunications satellites, covering communication areas in North, Central and Southern Africa, Asia and the Middle East, thus facilitating Turkish penetration in the framework of "soft power" in countries and regions of interest.

Ankara's continuous effort to create autonomy in terms of space capabilities is also aimed at gaining economic benefits and creating dependency relations with third countries to which space services will be provided. Therefore, it is expected that in the near future Turkey will seek to commercialize its space capabilities, as its ultimate goal is to become a country that will produce and launch satellites, exporting related technology and providing space services.

7. Challenges - Weaknesses

Despite its space ambitions, Turkey faces many challenges. Space exploration requires financial resources, high-tech infrastructure and a skilled workforce. Managing these costs while balancing other national priorities will be of key importance for Ankara.

The economic constraints resulting from the state of the Turkish economy (high inflation, continuous devaluation of the national currency, etc.) may have a negative impact on the funding of Turkey's space program, preventing it from achieving its objectives.

In addition, possible cooperation with China and Russia on the International Lunar Research Station could further complicate Turkey's relations with Western allies.

Overall, while Turkey is pursuing technological advancement and national prestige through its space program, its economic aspects and geopolitical alliances present challenges that could lead to friction with Western alliance partners.

8. Challenges for Greece

Turkey's space program is bound to pose challenges for Greece, at least at the military level.

The neutralization of Turkish satellites in wartime is considered impossible by Greece, since it is estimated that countries with high space technology capabilities such as the US, Russia, China, etc. have the ability to attack and destroy enemy satellites.

For this reason, it is estimated that measures should be considered to limit the impact of the satellite capabilities of the Turkish Armed Forces, such as:

- Locating and recording as far as possible the transit times of Turkish earth observation satellites over Greek territory, so that on the one hand our country's ED can

significantly limit the movement of forces and appropriate measures are taken to conceal military units and assets.

- Wide use of homologated weapons systems and assets.
- Meticulous concealment of weapon systems and means by appropriate means of camouflage, in order to make it difficult to identify them in terms of their number, deployment locations and type.
- Taking into account that in a period of operations part of the movements of military forces and means, due to the speed of the operations, will take place in good weather conditions and therefore may be perceived by the enemy, it is necessary in all phases of the battle and at all levels of command to plan and implement plans and actions of deception in order to create confusion for the enemy, difficulty in making a decision and fragmentation of his forces, which is necessary especially when facing an opponent with greater numerical strength.

9. Conclusions

The Turkish space policy is a long-term one, and has been a long-standing government priority since the 1990s, which, despite any delays, has been implemented consistently, at least in its main axes.

Turkey has maintained a largely harmonized national approach, characterized by a common vision and culture, and close cooperation between the relevant ministries, research organizations and the academic community, as well as the domestic and international aerospace industry.

Turkey's main objectives are to be present in all space themes, to be oriented towards serving foreign policy, security and defense needs and to strive for autonomy through indigenous design and production of satellite systems.

The main areas in which it has focused are the development of telecommunications, earth observation satellites and positioning-navigation satellites. These satellites have a dual use since they are used for both civil and military purposes.

The Turkish plan to develop space capabilities places particular emphasis on the training of personnel in order to create a 'pool' of qualified personnel and then to use them appropriately.

Turkey, in the context of its strategic objective to become a global power, has expanded the coverage area of its telecommunications satellites, covering communication areas in North, Central and Southern Africa, Asia and the Middle East, thus facilitating Turkish penetration in the framework of "soft power" in countries and regions of interest. Ankara's continuous effort to create autonomy in terms of space capabilities is also aimed at gaining economic benefits and creating dependency relations with third countries to which space services will be provided.

Given Turkey's capabilities in the space sector, the development of national space capabilities by Turkey in the field of communications and observation satellites and in the field of space in general is a one-way street, since space is gradually becoming, among other things, a new dimension of the unified battlefield, in order to compensate significantly for the advantages that the Turkish Armed Forces currently possess.

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Short Biography:

Lieutenant Colonel Panagiotis Katsaounis serves at Hellenic General Staff of the Army (HAGS) as an Intelligence Analyst. He has been trained in the fields of Intelligence Collection and Analysis, Counter-Intelligence, Cyber Defence, Counter-Terrorism and Strategic Communication.

In addition, he lectures as a military instructor on subjects related to his specializations at numerous Armed Forces Schools, such as the Army Land Warfare School, the Air Force Warfare School, etc.